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Research Article

**PHARMACIST-DRIVEN PATIENT EDUCATION AND ITS ROLE
IN HYPERTENSION MANAGEMENT AND COMPLICATION
PREVENTION IN TELANGANA****M Rohini, Sai Pawan A R, Shohidul Islam Mollah, Purasthu Srihitha, K. Vamshi,
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Abstract

Background: Hypertension is a major modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular diseases and their complications, affecting over a billion individuals worldwide and contributes to millions of preventable deaths annually.

Methodology: A prospective, observational, and interventional study was conducted in Telangana, India. Eligible hypertensive patients were enrolled after taking their consent and randomized into the control and test groups. The MARS-10 questionnaire (to assess medication adherence) and ASCVD risk estimator app (to estimate the cardiovascular risk) were administered to all patients at baseline to final follow-ups. Patients in the test group received pharmacist-led education at every follow-up, whereas the control group at the end of the study.

Results: 526 were enrolled and randomized into control and test group 265 (50.38%) and 261 (49.61%), respectively. In the current study, most of the patients were males (54.56%) with an age range of 30 to 70 years and belonged to the teaching profession (22.43%). Social history among most were social drinkers (57.22 %) and smokers (50.57%). In the control group, systolic BP (SBP), Diastolic BP (DBP), and pulse rate had no significant reduction, whereas in the test group, there was a significant reduction in SBP, DBP, and pulse rate from baseline to final follow-up. MARS scores and ASCVD scores had seen a significant improvement from baseline to final follow-up among test group patients with $p < 0.05$.

Conclusion: Pharmacist-led Education has shown a positive impact on Hypertension control and medication adherence behavior among test group patients.

Keywords: Hypertension, Medication adherence, Pharmacist-led Education, Risk Reduction.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension or high blood pressure refers to an elevated consistent blood pressure against the walls of your (blood vessels) arteries at 140/90 mm/Hg or higher ⁽¹⁾.

Circulation of blood will occur from the heart to various parts of the body through blood vessels. For every heartbeat, the blood enters into these vessels, creating pressure on the blood as the force of blood pushes against the walls of the arteries. The greater the pressure, the harder the heart must beat to pump blood ⁽²⁾.

Blood pressure (BP): Cardiac Output (CO) × Peripheral Resistance (PR)

The WHO 2023 Global report on Hypertension highlights the rising global burden of hypertension, particularly in the Asia Pacific and Southeast Asia regions, where prevalence has significantly increased over the past 30 years. Hypertension remains a leading cause of cardiovascular disease, stroke, and premature death, affecting over one billion people worldwide. However, only 54% of cases are diagnosed, 42% receive treatment, and 21% achieve blood pressure control. These alarming statistics emphasize the urgent need for improved screening, early diagnosis, and effective management strategies, strengthening primary healthcare systems and enhancing public awareness, ensuring access to affordable medication, and implementing lifestyle modifications to reduce hypertension-related complications. Addressing these challenges through policy interventions in healthcare improvements is essential to mitigate the global impact of hypertension. ⁽³⁾

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Methodology**

This prospective interventional study was conducted in the inpatient and outpatient departments of Mamatha Academy of Medical Sciences, Bachupally, Telangana, India, over 6 months. Hypertensive

patients (disease duration <4 years) meeting inclusion criteria were enrolled using block randomization. Patients with psychiatric illnesses, pregnancy, or severe illness were excluded.

A structured data collection form recorded patient demographics, education, social habits, socioeconomic status, past medical/medication history, family history, allergies, marital status, smoking, and alcohol status.

Medication adherence was assessed using the 10-item Medication Adherence Rating Scale (MARS). Scores range from 0 to 10, with higher scores indicating better adherence. The ASCVD Risk Estimator Plus App was used to assess cardiovascular risk. Lipid profile tests were conducted at baseline and final follow-up.

Patients were followed for 3 months with 30-day intervals. BP, pulse rate, and MARS scores were recorded at each visit. The test group received pharmacist-mediated structured education on disease, medication, diet, and lifestyle at baseline and follow-ups, along with a patient information leaflet. The control group received education only at the final follow-up.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 30.0.0.0. Wilcoxon signed-rank test assessed variations in MARS, ASCVD scores, lipid profiles, and complications from baseline to final follow-up. A p-value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 526 patients were enrolled from General Medicine, Ophthalmology, General Surgery, Orthopedics, Dermatology, Nephrology, and Pulmonology at MAMS Hospital. Details of enrolled patients are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS OF THE HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS

PARAMETER	CONTROL (n = 265)	TEST (n=261)
Gender	N (%)	N (%)
• Male	129(48.67)	158 (60.53)
• Female	136(51.32)	103(39.46)
Age		
• 30-40	46(17.35)	23(8.81)
• 41-50	50(18.86)	68(26.05)
• 51-60	90(33.96)	81(31.03)
• 61-70	79(29.81)	89(34.09)
Educational Qualification		
• Uneducated	28(10.56)	63(24.13)
• Primary school	84(31.69)	37(14.17)
• Secondary school	81(30.56)	62(23.75)
• Intermediate	3(1.13)	95(36.39)
• Graduate	69(26.03)	4(1.53)
Occupational Status		
• Farmer	22(8.30)	12(4.59)
• Daily wage worker	41(15.47)	71(27.20)
• Housewife	50(18.86)	35(13.40)
• Business	43(16.22)	0
• IT employee	5(1.88)	23(8.81)
• Teacher	42(15.84)	76(29.11)
• Engineer	52(19.62)	36(13.79)
• Others	10(3.77)	8(3.06)
Annual Income		
• 50,000-1,00,00	110(41.50)	149(57.08)
• 1,00,001-1,50,000	103(38.86)	105(40.22)
• 1,50,001-3,00,000	22(8.30)	0
• 3,00,001-5,00,000	10(3.77)	7(2.68)
• >5,00,000	20(7.54)	0
Marital Status		
• Single	0	24(9.19)
• Married	257(96.98)	219(83.90)
• Unmarried	8(3.01)	0
• Divorce	0	18(6.89)
Alcoholic Status		
• Non-alcoholic	98(36.98)	51(19.54)
• Social drinker	112(42.26)	189(72.41)
• Alcoholic	33(12.45)	21(8.04)
• Past alcoholic	22(8.31)	0
Smoking Status		
• Non- Smoker	159(60)	84(32.18)
• Smoker	89(33.58)	177(67.81)
• Past smoker	17(6.41)	0

The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula for an unlimited population. The required sample size was 385. The current study enrolled 589 patients. During the study period, 63 (12%) patients dropped out, resulting in a final sample size of 526 patients.

Out of 526 patients, 265 were randomized into the control group while 261 were randomized into the test group. The majority of the patients in the control group were 136 females (51.32%), whereas in the test group majority of the patients were 158 males (60.53%). This shows the data has been non-normally distributed.

The Mean \pm SD age of test group patients was 55.84 \pm 10.568 years, and that of the control group was 54.06 \pm 9.818 years. In the control group, the majority of the patients belonged to the age group of 51 to 60 years, i.e. 90 (33.96%), whereas in the test group, the majority of the patients belonged to the age group of 61 to 71 years, i.e. 89 (34.09%).

As per the educational qualification majority of the patients in the control group had education in primary school, 84 (31.69%), and in the test group education status among the majority of patients was Intermediate, 95 (36.39%). In the current study majority of the patients' occupations among the control group belonged to engineers 52 (19.62%), and in the test group, patients belonged to teaching, 76 (29.11%). The annual income of the majority of patients in the

control group was INR 50,000 - 1,00,000 (1 USD – 86.83 INR) i.e. 110 (41%) (1 USD – 86.83 INR). In the test group, the majority of patients' income was INR 50,000 - 1,00,000 (1 USD – 86.83 INR) i.e. 149 (57.08%).

The marital status of the enrolled patients in the control group was married 257 (96.98%), and in the test group was married 219 (83.90%).

The alcoholic status of the majority of the enrolled patients was, in the control group social drinker 112 (42.26%), and the test group social drinker 189 (72.41%).

The smoking status of the majority of the enrolled patients was, in the control group non-smoker 159 (60%) and in the test group, smoker 177 (67.81%). No of co-morbidities among the enrolled patients was in the control group majority of the patients had Diabetes Mellitus 64 (24.15%) and various other co-morbidities. In the test group majority of the patients' co-morbidity was Diabetes Mellitus 47 (18%).

As per the diagnosis, the majority of the patients in the control group had been diagnosed with uncontrolled hypertension, 56 (21.13%) followed by various other diagnosis

Among test group patients, the majority of the patients were diagnosed with hypertension 69 (26.43%) followed by various other diagnosis.

MEDIAN PULSE RATE AMONG CONTROL AND TEST GROUP

Figure 1: Median pulse rate among the control and test groups

Pulse rate was measured for all the enrolled patients at various follow-ups from baseline to final follow-up. There was a significant reduction in pulse rate among test group patients from 90 to 76 by the end of the follow-up, i.e., $p < 0.001$, whereas in the control, there was no significant reduction in pulse rate throughout all follow-ups, i.e. $p > 0.88$. The details of the median pulse rate among the control and test groups are presented in Figure 1.

MEDIAN SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE BETWEEN THE FOLLOW-UPS AMONG THE CONTROL AND TEST GROUPS:

Figure 2: Median systolic blood pressure among control and test group

Systolic blood pressure was measured for all the enrolled patients at various follow-ups from baseline to final follow-up. There was a significant reduction in systolic blood pressure among test group patients from 160mmHg to 120mmHg by the end of the follow-up with $p < 0.001$, whereas in the control, there was no significant reduction in systolic blood pressure throughout all follow-ups, i.e $p > 0.12$. The details of the median systolic blood pressure among the control and test groups are presented in Figure 2.

MEDIAN DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE BETWEEN THE FOLLOW-UPS AMONG THE CONTROL AND TEST GROUPS

Figure 3: Median diastolic blood pressure among control and test groups

Diastolic blood pressure was measured for all the enrolled patients at various follow-ups from baseline to final follow-up. There was a significant reduction in diastolic blood pressure among test group patients from 100mmHg to 80mmHg by the end of the follow-up with $p < 0.001$, whereas in the control, there was no significant reduction in diastolic blood pressure throughout all follow-ups, i.e, $p > 0.98$. The details of the median diastolic blood pressure among the control and test groups are presented in Figure 3.

MEDIAN LIPID PROFILE VALUES AMONG THE CONTROL AND TEST GROUPS

The lipid profile test was performed for all the enrolled patients at baseline and the final follow-up. There was a significant reduction in lipid profile values among test group patients from (LDL- 150 mg/dL to 100 mg/dL, VLDL – 50mg/dL to 33mg/dL, and TG- 240mg/dL to 170mg/dL) by end of the follow-up i.e $p < 0.001$. whereas in the control, there was no significant reduction in lipid profile value throughout all follow-ups, i.e., $p > 0.05$.

COMPARISON OF ASCVD SCORES BETWEEN THE FOLLOW-UPS AMONG THE CONTROL AND TEST GROUPS:

The ASCVD Apps were used to estimate a patient's risk of developing cardiovascular disease in both groups at baseline, second, and final follow-up. A significant improvement in ASCVD Scores was observed in the test group patients ($p < 0.001$) compared to that of the control group patients ($p > 0.05$). The findings are presented in 2.

Table 2: Comparison of ASCVD between the follow-ups among the control and test groups:

ASCVD Scores	CONTROL		TEST	
	Z -value	P-value	Z -value	P-value
ASCVD ₀ -ASCVD ₃	9.699	1.000	-13.504	< 0.001**

*Wilcoxon signed the rank test

**significant at ≤ 0.05 level

Here, the ASCVD₀ denotes the baseline and ASCVD₃ denotes the final follow-up.

Median ASCVD scores baseline to final follow-up among the control and test groups

Figure 4: Median ASCVD scores baseline to final follow-up among control and test group

ASCVD score was estimated for all the enrolled patients at baseline and the final follow-up. There was a significant reduction in ASCVD scores among test group patients from 29% to 10% by the end of the follow-up, i.e. $p < 0.001$,

whereas in the control, there was no significant reduction in ASCVD scores throughout all follow-ups, i.e., $p > 1.00$. The details of the median ASCVD scores among the control and test groups are presented in Figure 2.

The cardiovascular complications assessment was used to evaluate the patient's cardiovascular risk in both groups at baseline, second, and final follow-up. A significant improvement was observed in the test group patients ($p < 0.001$) compared to that of the control group patients ($p > 0.05$).

Median MARS score from baseline to final follow-up among the control and test groups

Figure 5: Median MARS score from baseline to final follow-up among control and test groups

MARS scores were estimated for all the enrolled patients at various follow-ups from baseline to final follow-up. At the start (Baseline), both groups had low adherence, with MARS scores of 3 (30%) and 3 (30%) among the control and test groups, respectively. By the final follow-up, the control group's medication adherence knowledge remained unchanged while significant improvement was seen in the test group, from 3 (30%) to 9 (90%).

DISCUSSION:

The WHO Global Report on Hypertension (2023) highlights a growing burden of hypertension, especially in the Asia Pacific and Southeast Asia regions, over the past 30 years. Over 1 billion people are affected globally, yet only 54% are diagnosed, 42% treated, and just 21% achieve control. Hypertension remains a key driver of cardiovascular disease, stroke, and premature mortality. The study concluded that a need for enhanced screening, early diagnosis, public awareness, stronger primary care systems, accessible treatment, and lifestyle interventions. Strengthening health policies is critical to mitigate the ongoing impact. ⁽³⁾

The current study found that Pharmacists led Education in improving blood pressure control and reducing cardiovascular risk among hypertensive patients.

A total of 526 patients were enrolled; the majority were males 287(54.56%), and females, 239 (45.43%). The number of patients was more in the age group of 51 to 70 years when compared with other age groups. In a similar Study, 47.8% were males, and 52.2% were females and the number of subjects was more in the age group of 50-65 years when compared with other age groups. ⁽⁴⁾

In the control group, the majority of patients 84 (31.69%) had completed primary school education whereas in the test group, most patients 95(36.39%) had an intermediate-level education. These differences in educational background may influence health awareness treatment adherence and overall health outcomes. In a similar study as most of the patients were illiterate, it was difficult for them to remember of names of the drugs, but on repeated counseling, they remembered it with the help of the strips, color, and covers of the medicines which made them adhere to their medication properly. ⁽⁵⁾

In the control group systolic BP (SBP), Diastolic BP (DBP), and pulse rate had no significant reduction, whereas in the test group, there was a significant reduction in SBP, DBP, and pulse rate from baseline to final follow-up.

CONCLUSION:

Pharmacist-led education significantly ($P < 0.05$) improves patients' Medication Adherence Knowledge (MARS) about hypertension control and reduces the risk of cardiovascular complications in the test group patients. This study demonstrates that pharmacist intervention significantly reduced median Systolic Blood Pressure and Diastolic Blood Pressure and improved medication adherence and knowledge of hypertensive patients. The overall study findings confirmed the need for pharmacist intervention in Hospitals to improve hypertension control and cardiovascular disease management.

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